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**Hermeneutical Approaches to Biblical
Studies in African Context**

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Abstract

African biblical hermeneutics is the re-reading of the Christian scripture from a premeditatedly Afrocentric perspective. Biblical Studies in African context is an amalgamation of multiple interpretive methods, approaches and foci that reflect a creative engagement of the African cosmological reality and the bible. Majority of African Christians predominantly use Eurocentric cosmology and *anglo saxon* as an official language of interpretation of the bible to the detriment of Afrocentric hermeneutics. The onus of this paper is an evaluation of Afrocentric interpretation of the Bible in African context. Descriptive analysis method was used to carry out this research which focuses on the development of African Biblical Hermeneutics in the region of African nations, namely: Central Africa, Eastern Africa, Horn of Africa, Southern Africa and Western Africa. Findings show that, Biblical Studies in Africa is characterized as both innovative and reactionary. Conclusively, African biblical hermeneutics is contextual since interpretation is always done in a particular context. Therefore, the analysis of the biblical text should be done from the perspective of an African world-view and culture. It recommended therefore that African Biblical Scholars and Hermeneutics should lay more emphasis on the interpretation of the bible in Afrocentric cosmology and languages in textual analysis of the scripture instead of Eurocentricism.

Keywords: Africa, Biblical Studies, Culture, Eurocentricism, Hermeneutics

Introduction

African biblical hermeneutics is a methodological resource that makes African social cultural contexts the subject of interpretation. This is a methodology that reappraises ancient biblical tradition and African world-views, cultures and life experiences, with the purpose of correcting the effect of the cultural, ideological conditioning to which Africa and Africans have been subjected in the business of biblical interpretation. It is the rereading of the Christian scripture from a premeditatedly Afrocentric perspective. African biblical hermeneutics is contextual since interpretation is always done in a particular context. Specifically, it means that the analysis of the biblical text is done from the perspective of an African world-view and culture.

In the history of biblical interpretation, four major types of hermeneutics have emerged: the literal, moral, allegorical and anagogical. Literal interpretation asserts that a biblical text is to be interpreted according to the “plain meaning” conveyed by its grammatical construction and historical context. Interpretation of Scripture occurs within one's worldview and culture, which enhances our understanding and ability to apply Scripture in the world. However, few books address Bible interpretation from an African perspective and no other textbook uses the intercultural approach found here.

The term ‘hermeneutics’ traditionally refers to the study of how one interprets a text or work of art; while works on hermeneutics in this broader sense are helpful for reading the Bible. The Bible has been read in Africa since the apostolic age. The history of Christianity in Africa could be written as the story of African readers understanding, translating, interpreting, explaining and applying the teachings of the Bible. Nevertheless, with the exception of the section on Ethiopian hermeneutics, this article focuses on the main developments that have taken place in English-speaking African Biblical Hermeneutics since the middle of the twentieth century. This article focuses on resources that relate more directly to ‘biblical hermeneutics, that is, the study of how one interprets biblical texts. This branch of knowledge includes both the general principles that guide biblical study and the specific methods that are used.

Most of the biblical interpretation in Africa is done by ordinary Christians or church leaders at the ‘grassroots’ level, for example, in worship, prayer

and preaching. Thus, biblical hermeneutics is not limited to academic study or even written forms of interpretation, it encompasses both verbal and non-verbal communication. Given the variety of resources available, this article uses the term biblical hermeneutics to refer to both theories of interpretation, such as inculturation hermeneutics, and the principles and methods implicit in practices of interpretation, such as those found in African Independent Churches. With the exception of the Ethiopian tradition, which traces its origins back to the early church, African biblical interpretation is characterised by a strong awareness of the distance between imported readings of the biblical text and the African reader. Western missionaries brought their own Western readings of the Bible to African contexts, with the result many African readers faced a 'double' hermeneutical gap when approaching the biblical text: between ancient texts and the contemporary situation and between Western readings and African realities.

In response, African biblical interpreters have developed their own readings of the Bible to better address the lives of African Christians. Comparative approaches have emphasised the similarities between biblical and African cultural contexts. Furthermore, the African cultural context has come to be seen as a valuable resource for biblical study. These developments have been accompanied by a growing realisation of the importance of the cultural and social location of the reader in biblical interpretation. In a number of ways, African readers may be much better placed than Western readers to understand the Bible in African context.

The word Bible is derived from the Greek word *Biblion* meaning *a book*. This is the name used in describing the holy book of the Jews and Christians containing the word of God recorded by Holy men inspired by the Holy Spirit. The Holy Bible is known by other titles such as *the scripture*, *the writing*, *The Word of God*, etc Luke 4:17, Mark 12:10 and Hebrew. 4:12. In fact, there are some unique features that distinguish the Bible from other type of books, source and authorship reasons for various translations and some other books are not included in the common versions of the Bible.

Facts about the Bible

Bible, although it is a library, (as Jerome) named the Bible as the divine library in 4th Century A. D. The Bible is a story, a grand story that moves on from commencement to the end. In the Bible all together, these subjects are found:

- (a) Law – in the books of Moses called Pentateuch
- (b) History – in Samuel, Kings, Chronicles and other books
- (c) Philosophy – in the books of Job and Ecclesiastics
- (d) Poetry – in the Psalms and Songs of Solomon
- (e) Prophecy – in Isaiah, Jeremiah, Ezekiel and the Minor Prophets
- (f) Doctrine – in the Epistles
- (g) Revelations – in the Apocalypse and Daniel
- (h) Geography – in the book of Acts, etc.

The Bible unlike others books, a divine revelation, a progressive revelation, a revelation of God to man, communicated through men, moves on smoothly from its beginning to its great end. The Bible history takes one back to the unknown past of eternity, and its prophecies takes us into the otherwise unknown future.

The Bible represents the word of God to the world but came in culture of a particular people who got the message and expressed it in ways intelligible to them. It is necessary to find relevant ways of bringing the Bible message to the African languages. This enables the gospel of Jesus to be expressed and applied in a variety of ways using African languages to the Africans. Christian message provides the answer to the questions implied in human existence.

African Countries with Christianity as the Religion of the Majority

Rank	Country	Region	% of national population affiliated to Christianity
1	Sao tome and Principe	Central Africa	97.0
2	Democratic Republic of the Congo	Central Africa	95.8
3	Angola	Central Africa	95.0
4	Rwanda	East Africa	93.6
5	Seychelles	East Africa	93.1
6	Equatorial Guinea	Central Africa	93.0
7	Lesotho	Southern Africa	90.0
8	Namibia	Southern Africa	90.0

9	Swaziland	Southern African	90.0
10	Zambia	East Africa	87.0
11	Republic of the Congo	Central Africa	85.9
12	Liberia	West Africa	85.5
13	Cape Verde	West Africa	85.0
14	Reunion	East Africa	84.9
15	Uganda	East Africa	84.0
16	Zimbabwe	Southern Africa	84.0
17	Central African Republic	Central Africa	80.3
18	Malawi	East Africa	79.9
19	South Africa	Southern Africa	79.7
20	Kenya	East Africa	78.0
21	Burundi	East Africa	75.0
22	Gabon	Central Africa	73.0
23	Botswana	Southern Africa	71.6
24	Ghana	West Africa	71.2
25	Cameroon	Central Africa	69.2
26	Ethiopia	Horn of Africa	62.8
27	Eritrea	Horn of Africa	62.5
28	Tanzania	East Africa	61.4
29	South Sudan	East Africa	60.5
30	Nigeria	West Africa	58.0
31	Mozambique	East Africa	56.1

Source: Parrinder 1969

Biblical Inculturation

According to Omoyeni and Arthur (2013), Biblical Studies in Africa does not simply take the questions, methods, presuppositions and interpretations that have been arrived at in the western world and uncritically appropriate them in African biblical settings. Rather, Biblical studies in Africa is borne out of the African biblical scholar engaging the Bible free (or as free as possible) of any trappings of western hermeneutical presuppositions and interests. Dube and West (2000) noted that Nigerian Justin Ukpong

characterizes the lynchpin of African biblical interpretation as ‘an encounter between the Biblical text and the African context’ that is not hesitant to address the past, present and future in light of the biblical text. So, Biblical studies in Africa takes both the African and the biblical realities as equal partners in *dialogue*, resulting in a distinctive juxtaposition of questions, approaches and interpretations.

Gerald West, a South African biblical scholar, agrees and is emphatic that Biblical Studies in Africa remain integral to the larger discipline of African theology: ‘The separation of biblical studies from other theological disciplines, so common elsewhere, cannot be allowed to happen in an African biblical study.’ West noted that Africa was on the verge of an African biblical scholarship discipline that he maintained would and should look distinct from the biblical studies that has been predominant in the west.

The intent would not be to reject the grammatical-historical and literary studies that have dominated biblical studies in the west, but to recognize that, as African theologians have said, western theological education remains fairly sterile in addressing African concerns. Therefore, even when western methods are utilized by African biblical scholars, they are incorporated into a creative impulse that even original proponents may never have envisioned.

Paradoxically, majority of the African biblical scholars in the last half century or so have been trained in western academies. When Norwegian K. (2002) analysed 87 Old Testament/Hebrew Bible dissertations written by African scholars between 1967 and 2000, the majority of those written in western institutions did not bring the African backgrounds or contexts to bear on the writing.

G. West’s sentiments echo perspectives proposed by earlier African theologians, probably best articulated by Kwesi Dickson of Ghana (1984). While Dickson wants to separate ‘culture’ and ‘religion’, it seems unnecessary, since in both the biblical and the African worldviews the cultural and the religious are so closely entwined that all aspects of life have religious meaning. Biblical Studies in Africa thus incorporates all spheres of life in its purview (Meenan 2014). To this, West (2008) adds the need to have a live African interpreter (African-ness unspecified), and also the need to distinguish between the scholar and the ‘ordinary’ reader who in essence is any African person, not a fictive personality, and who reads beside the trained African biblical scholar. According to Loba-Mkole and Wendland (2005), this distinction is important for West as he points out the fact that

under South African apartheid, the African communities were denied a hearing, formal education and political rights, which effectively silenced them. This is a reading 'with' the ordinary reader, and not reading 'on behalf of' the ordinary reader.

Overall, then, Biblical Studies in Africa refuses to deal with the Bible simply as an ancient text and demands that it be engaged to deal with present concerns, addressing issues that resonate with African (and world) realities. Accordingly, Biblical Studies in Africa embraces more than just exegetical interests but privileges hermeneutical concerns (Villa-Vicencio 1992). For example, Musa Dube's (2000) groundbreaking study, *Postcolonial Feminist Interpretation of the Bible*, while classified as biblical studies, draws from a wide array of disciplines including African philosophy, African literary studies, and study of African religions, and unapologetically incorporates them under the rubric of a new discipline, Postcolonial Feminist Biblical Studies. This process has remained constant in Biblical studies in Africa, having been christened initially more positively as *inculturation* (Ukpong 1995), and more recently as *decolonization* (Abogunrin, 2005) of the biblical text from western imperialism.

According to Ukpon (1999) African biblical scholars have a tendency to gravitate to texts that are not only relevant to their African reality, but which may not usually be in the purview of western biblical scholars (e.g., texts on polygamy, healing, spirits, etc.). As African philosophers Mudimbe and Kilonzo (2012) explain, this process of 'Africanization is a post-colonial phenomenon concerned with adapting modalities of belief and rethinking of rituals. Christian independency challenges colonial representations of ways of believing'.

Furthermore, African biblical scholars perceive a deeper paradigm: in the same way that Christianity was shaped by its encounter with the Gentile Greco-Roman world (Acts 15; Galatians) from its origins as a Jewish sect called 'the Way' (Acts 9.2), African biblical scholars see the encounter with African contexts as a watershed moment in the shaping of Christianity beyond the African context (Mofokeng 1987). Some of the western scholars who have seen potential benefit of this aspect of Biblical Studies in Africa reckon a possibility of 'a reading with ethical accountability' in biblical studies fostered by African Biblical Studies' demand to emphasize the present (Burridge 2007).

Nevertheless, this argument has not gone without detractors who have felt that perhaps the African background was being uncritically and

overzealously appropriated by African theologians. In this camp, Nigeria's Byang Kato's writing is probably the best known, even though there are others like Burkina Faso's Tite Tienou (1984), who also offer similar criticism. In his strongly dissenting *Theological Pitfalls in Africa*, Kato bemoaned what he saw as too much exultation of 'African culture, philosophy and religion beyond proportion'. Such criticism, however, fails to perceive the fact that it perpetuates the colonialist negative evaluation of the ways that African religious cosmology communicates realities about the Christian God. It also fails to be cognizant of the fact that the African religious reality is entrenched in the entirety of the African reality and inevitably seeps through any African theological construction, inadvertently or otherwise.

The issue of inculturation of Biblical studies in Africa and who can do the inculturation is a question that lingers. For instance, can non-Africans do African biblical interpretation? Ukpong (1999) has rightly maintained that the incorporation of African elements into the historical and literary readings of the Bible is what allows for African biblical interpretation to arrive at distinct conclusions from those made by western counterparts on the same texts. In this regard, then, it would seem that it is the African content that determines whether a writing is engaging in African biblical interpretation.

Historic Overview of Biblical Studies in Africa

Biblical Studies in Africa is connected in complex ways to Christianity in Africa. The origins of Christianity in Africa remain debated. Some scholars point to its biblical beginnings (e.g., the conversion of the Ethiopian eunuch in Acts 8.26-39), while others identify Christianity's origins with the arrival of European missionaries in the African continent, south of the Sahara, starting in the fifteenth century (Isichei 1995). The former see a tradition running through such significant Christian figures as Augustine, Origen and Tertullian, among others, as the true fathers of Biblical Studies in Africa (Ngong 2012). Opponents point out that this form of Christianity never spread beyond Egypt, Ethiopia, and Nubia in northeastern Africa.

Either way, current African biblical scholarship is neither simply a product of western missionary evangelizing in Africa nor a totally independent African formulation (Ngong 2012). The development of a distinctly scholarly African theological reflection in the last fifty years of post-colonialism has been primarily driven by African theologians grappling with concerns in

their specific African contexts, utilizing scholarship learned in or borrowed from the west. There are two primary streams that have developed in this process: (1) reclaiming of positive values of African religious realities as foundations of an authentic African Christianity, and (2) construction of a biblical response to contemporary concerns of African communities.

According to Gerald West, African biblical Scholars have turned tools acquired from the west 'against the damage done by western missionary and colonial forces.' The arrival of missionaries in Africa, while crucial for the growth of Christianity in Africa, was also inextricably bound to European imperialism and colonialism (Sanneh, 1989). And even though the wave of European missionary activity in Sub-Saharan Africa, with their Christian schools, church plantings, and Bible translations into local African languages, no doubt helped establish Christianity in the continent over time, perhaps the most portent instruments of Christian expansion were primarily African converts who evangelized other Africans (Oliver, 1992).

The following thematic and periodic outline is not meant to imply that these were the only methods in their respective time spans or that there are no overlaps. Rather, it is a heuristic tool for sorting through the diverse field of methods and foci that have characterized Biblical Studies in Africa. The interplay between Biblical Studies in Africa and the historical and political realities, especially of the post-independence periods, is meant to highlight the tendency of Africa Biblical Studies to focus on the present in contrast to the ancient.

Impositions of Colonizers Interpretations

The colonial period is between 1880s and 1980s. The beginning of colonization on the African continent is usually set around the infamous Berlin conference of 1884 that saw European powers (largely Holland, Belgium, England, France, Portugal, and Spain) subdivide among themselves the African continent for European conquest and occupation. Musa Dube maintains that at the core of both the imposition of colonialism and the subsequent work for African political independence was a struggle founded on the appropriation, interpretation and application of the Bible. Colonial formal education was subsequently set up to do two things through two mechanisms: (1) missionary schools aimed to provide the African converts with the ability to read the Bible for themselves (or so they claimed), and (2) government schools sought to produce a colonial workforce only at the clerical level at best.

The Bible was viewed by Africans as complicit in the colonial process in at least two ways: (1) as official religion of the colonizers, it provided the grounds for an African religious genocide, and (2) it gave theological support to military subjugation of Africans in the guise of Christianization. The collusion (intentional or not) of European missionaries and colonial administrators solidified, for the colonized, the imperializing role of the Bible as part of the colonial project, even as, paradoxically, the Africans converted to Christianity (Mbuvi, 2014).

A statement of unclear origin, but attributed to Kenya's first president Mzee Jomo Kenyatta, encapsulates this interplay between the Bible and colonialism in Africa: 'When the Missionaries arrived, the Africans had the Land and the Missionaries had the Bible. They taught us how to pray with our eyes closed. When we opened our eyes, they had the land and we had the Bible' (Walker, 2002). Thus, the general perspective of the European missionaries to Africa was a kind of schizophrenia between a deep 'Christian' compassion for the Africans as peoples (or a hoodwinking of the people using the Bible), and a deep disdain and judgment, based on the same Christian convictions, of Africa cultural religious reality. The latter was judged to be evil, satanic, primitive, and so on.

Conversion to Christianity for Africans under European missionaries, as a result, usually meant abandonment of everything African and an embrace of everything European (Anderson, 1970). And even the most sympathetic of European missionaries to African cultures seemed only to find the redeemable elements in African communities to be those that could find parallel or resemblance in the Bible or western philosophical structures (Tempels, 1959).

The colonial period's subjugation of African peoples involved indoctrination of the African subjects to European methodologies that aligned with the European interpretations of the Bible. Not only was the Bible used as a means of justifying the presence of the missionaries (and subsequently colonialists), it was also used to pacify the colonized (Memmi, 1965). As J.B. Stanfield explains, 'while academic education was to be given to European and Asian children, African children were to receive industrial and agricultural training. Christian teaching became compulsory and African customs and traditions were subsequently neglected'. When, in response, Africans formed African independent schools that would allow aspects of African culture and realities to be part of education, they were promptly shut down by the colonialists on the pretext that Africans did not have the

financial and organizational skills to run educational institutions (Stanfield, 2005). The result was a systemic erosion and exorcising of African cultural and religious reality from among the early converts to Christianity, essentially forcing them to adopt European languages, cultures and values as a means of becoming Christians. In essence, the early African convert to Christianity could only read and interpret the Bible from the standpoint of the European colonizer, resulting in awkwardly Europeanized renditions of Bibles, hymnbooks, catechetical material, ecclesiastical groups and forms of worship (Baeta 1968).

Translations of Bible into African Languages

Bible translations into African languages started with European missionaries in the 1800s and continue today with such organizations as a global faith none profit that works with local community around the world to develop language solution that expand possibility for a better life, largely run by a mix of local native translators with some support from nonnative 'experts' (Noss, 2007). The driving force was a desire to have the Bible available in the African languages for the new converts. African biblical scholars have highlighted some of the problems caused by cultural blindness that early translations created in African theological thinking (Mbuwayesango, 2001). On the other hand, Lamin Sanneh's (1989) has argued that there were fortuitous and unforeseen benefits of European led Bible translations into African languages, maintaining that the translations formed the nexus of independent theological formulations that were eventually to result in both indigenous African Churches and a distinct African theology.

Building on Sanneh's propositions, Bible translation has been shown to have generated authentic African biblical interpretations by allowing the reading of the Bible in African mother-tongues and within the sphere of African cosmological reality (Bediako, 1996; Gathogo and Kinyua, 2010). Translations into African languages allowed the African reader freedom to make associations with their African linguistic and social realities in interpretation of the Bible independent of the encumbrances of reading it in a foreign language thus arriving at authentically African biblical readings (Mojola, 2007).

Construction of African Christian Identity

It is no surprise that following the political independence of African countries from European colonialism starting in the late 1950s through the 1980s, recovery/ redemption of the African cultural-religious past became the primary focus of African theologians (Idowu, 1962). Political independence seemed to motivate African theologians to construct an African Christian identity that not only removed the stigma placed on African religious reality by European missionaries but also make it foundational in formulating an African Christianity that was also both uncompromisingly African and authentically Christian (Bediako, 1996).

Consequently, African theological projects sought to establish the inherent compatibility of African religious reality to the Bible message by arguing that African concepts of God were intrinsically monotheistic (Idowu 1962), theorizing that the concept of life after death (the living-dead) in African religions was compatible with the Christian concept of resurrection (Mbiti, 1975), maintaining that the African belief in spirits was consistent with the biblical belief in spirits and demons (Green, 1995), and more. This 'hermeneutic of rehabilitation', or 'hermeneutic of resonance', between African realities and the biblical text (Green, 1995) became a primary occupation of the African theologians from then on.

The different emphases in interpretation, are not merely due to personal situatedness, but also stem from deep theological beliefs about God, creation, humanity, revelation and salvation. Grouping the approaches according to interpretive tradition or movement helps to make these theological assumptions more explicit. First, there are sections on the Ethiopian tradition and the African Independent Church movement. Next, there are 'classic' approaches in African Christian Theology, including Inculturation and Intercultural hermeneutics, Liberation and Black hermeneutics, Feminist and Women's hermeneutics, and Contextual Bible Study and Ordinary Readers' hermeneutics. These are followed by a section on the Pentecostal movement. The article concludes with more recent approaches, such as Reconstruction, Postcolonial and Mother Tongue hermeneutics.

For some of the luminaries of African theological scholarship such as John Mbiti and Mulago gwa Cikala (followed by Bediako 1996), it became fundamentally crucial to not only recover African religions as complex and sophisticated systems in and of themselves, but also to show their preparatory nature for the Gospel message. In this regard, African religions

were perceived as equivalents of the Old Testament, preparing the African for the arrival of the Gospel of Jesus Christ (*praeparatio evangelica*) (Cikala 1965): 'In missiological jargon, these [African] Traditional Religions will have been a real *praeparatio evangelica* (preparation for the Gospel); and it is now up to African theologians to interpret the meaning of that preparation for the Gospel in the African context of not only the past, but today and tomorrow' (Mbiti 1970b: 36).

Conclusion

Biblical Studies in Africa is a product of biblical compilation. This survey began from the bible. The bible represents the word of God sent to the world of which the African Biblical scholars expressed and applied in African languages to the African Christian.

Biblical Studies in Africa grows in its adherents and increasingly gain credence with biblical scholars beyond African biblical scholarship. Its contributions become more apparent. This article highlights the contributions it adds to Biblical Studies by challenging certain Western readings of the Bible and shows distinctive interpretive approaches that introduce new perspectives in interpreting the Bible.

This paper recommends that the Biblical Studies in Africa should be more encouraged among the African Bible scholarship. African church denominations also need to be deeper in interpreting biblical messages in their local tongues. The focus on the present in Biblical Studies in Africa should be seen as complimentary, pushing for all-round exegesis and hermeneutics.

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